

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF ENDOMETRIAL HYPERPLASIA IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE

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ABSTRACT

Endometrial hyperplasia is a common gynecological pathology among women of reproductive age. According to various studies, it is detected in approximately 20–30% of women who seek medical care due to abnormal uterine bleeding. If this condition is not treated in a timely manner, especially in atypical forms, the risk of developing endometrial cancer increases in 8–29% of cases. In addition, endometrial hyperplasia may lead to infertility, severe uterine bleeding, and anemia, which significantly worsen reproductive health in women of reproductive age.

Research objective: To study the clinical characteristics of endometrial hyperplasia in women of reproductive age.

Materials and methods: The study was conducted using a retrospective observational method. The study group consisted of 50 female patients aged 20–45 years who were treated in the gynecology department. Clinical, laboratory, and instrumental examination results were analyzed based on the patients' medical records. During the study, the patients' age, body mass index (BMI), characteristics of the menstrual cycle, the presence of abnormal uterine bleeding, endometrial thickness according to ultrasound examination, and histological examination results were studied. The obtained data were processed using variation-statistical methods, and the results were evaluated based on comparative analysis.

Results: According to the study results, endometrial hyperplasia was found to occur more frequently in women aged 30–45 years. Among the 50 patients included in the study, 22 (44%) had menstrual cycle disorders, while 35 (70%) experienced abnormal uterine bleeding. Analysis also revealed that 18 patients (36%) had obesity, 15 (30%) had anovulatory cycles, and 12 (24%) were diagnosed with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), indicating that these conditions are important risk factors for the development of the disease. Ultrasonographic examination showed that endometrial thickening ranged from 7–18 mm in most patients. Specifically, endometrial thickness was 7–10 mm in 21 patients (42%), 11–14 mm in 19 patients (38%), and 15–18 mm in 10 patients (20%). These results demonstrate that endometrial thickening is one of the key diagnostic features of endometrial hyperplasia in women of reproductive age. Histological examination confirmed the presence of endometrial hyperplasia in the studied cases.

Conclusion: Endometrial hyperplasia is an important precancerous condition that negatively affects reproductive health in women of reproductive age and increases the risk of

developing endometrial cancer. Early detection of the disease, regular monitoring of women in risk groups, and timely treatment are of great preventive importance. Regular ultrasound monitoring of women in high-risk groups and appropriate treatment can reduce complications of the disease and help prevent the development of endometrial cancer.

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